

AGGLOMERATION ISSUES IN CITY PLANNING AND CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract: This article covers the main issues faced in urban agglomerations and their planning. For the sustainable development of urban agglomerations, an efficient transport system, ecological infrastructure and planned territorial expansion are necessary. The article analyzes the difficulties associated with the growth of agglomeration areas, the development of infrastructure and transport networks in the case of large cities of Uzbekistan, including Tashkent and Samarkand. New agglomeration approaches, creation of green zones and improvement of public transport systems are proposed in the planning of the cities of Uzbekistan. The article highlights the global and local problems faced in the process of urbanization and offers strategic solutions for the development of agglomerations.

Key words: Agglomeration, transport and infrastructure, Ecology, Social infrastructure,

Introduction

Agglomeration and urban planning is one of the most urgent issues of world urban planning today. As cities become the center of economic and demographic development, the surrounding areas are also growing rapidly under the influence of urbanization. In particular, the increase in population, the development of industry and the expansion of the transport system accelerate this process. Therefore, the problem of planning agglomeration areas and their sustainable development has become an important topic not only for architects, but also for public administration systems and economists. This article is devoted to the definition of agglomeration processes, their impact on planning and construction processes in cities, current issues and proposed solutions in the case of Uzbekistan.

What is agglomeration?

An agglomeration is a territorial structure consisting of a large city and its surrounding small towns and villages, united by economic, social and transport links. This process usually occurs as a result of the natural expansion of cities and is directly related to economic development. As large cities become major production and service centers, many new areas for living and working are emerging around them. The process of agglomeration can occur not only as a result of natural growth, but also as a result of planned political and economic measures.

Agglomeration Issues in Urban Planning

Agglomeration creates a number of problems in urban planning. One of the main reasons for this is related to maintaining the identity of the villages and towns around the city and managing their economic dependence on the city. At the same time, preservation of ecological balance in agglomeration areas, efficient organization of transport and infrastructure systems also require great attention.

Effective organization of transport systems in agglomeration areas is a big problem. The increasing flow of traffic to big cities creates traffic jams, which creates problems for people living in and around the

city. In order to improve the transport system, first of all, it is necessary to strengthen the connection between large and small cities, develop public transport systems and improve road transport infrastructure.

Industrial development and population growth in big cities increase environmental problems. Air pollution and the continuous reduction of green areas have a negative impact on the sustainable development of cities. Therefore, it is important to take environmental factors into account and expand green zones in the planning of agglomeration areas.

Research results

Along with the increase in population in agglomeration areas, social infrastructure, i.e. schools, hospitals, shopping centers and other public facilities should also increase. Poor planning of this process can lead to a decrease in the quality of life of the population. Therefore, social infrastructure systems should be implemented together with development plans of agglomeration areas.

Agglomeration processes have significantly increased in the cities of Uzbekistan. Especially the areas around Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara and other big cities are rapidly becoming urbanized. In the example of Tashkent, in recent years, due to the lack of a master plan, irregular constructions have been carried out around the city, and this has seriously burdened the city's infrastructure.

Although the city of Tashkent was rebuilt on the basis of the master plan after the 1966 earthquake, today this plan is quite outdated and needs to be updated. In recent years, many empty areas of the city have been built without planning, which has a negative impact on the city's infrastructure and transport system. Due to the lack of a master plan, the original image of the city is also disappearing.

Urban Agglomerations Include A Large City And Its Adjoining Outgrowths

1-Fig..

The city of Samarkand is also distinguished by its agglomeration development. The increase in the population and the emergence of new industrial areas have put a serious burden on the city's infrastructure. The unplanned growth of many new areas of Samarkand has a negative impact on the original image of the city.

Solutions of Agglomeration Development

1. Long-term master plans. It is necessary to develop a long-term master plan for each large city and its surrounding agglomeration areas. These plans determine the directions of future development of cities and make it possible to plan infrastructure, ecology, transport and social infrastructure systems.

2. Maintaining ecological balance. In the agglomeration development of cities, maintaining ecological balance and expanding green areas is of great importance. This not only improves the ecological situation, but also creates healthy and comfortable living conditions for the population.

It is necessary to develop the public transport system and expand road networks in order to eliminate the problems of traffic and transport infrastructure in large cities. For this, it is necessary to use modern technologies, optimize traffic flows and strengthen intercity transport connections.

Conclusion

Agglomeration processes are one of the most urgent issues in urban planning in today's urbanization era. The disorderly development of cities not only damages the infrastructure and ecology, but also creates social and economic problems. In Uzbekistan, in particular, these problems can be solved by updating the master plans of cities such as Tashkent and Samarkand and developing long-term strategies for agglomeration areas.

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